

Sterols from marine green algae of Indian waters

A. K. Siddhanta*, A. M. Goswami, M. Shanmugam, K. H. Mody and B. K. Ramavat

Marine Algae and Marine Environment Discipline, Central Salt and Marine Chemicals Research Institute, Bhavnagar-364 002, India

E-mail : salt@csir.res.in Fax : 091-0278-566970/567562

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A sterol glycoside (3-O- β -D-galactopyranosylclerosterol, 1a) and clerosterol (24-ethylcholesta-5,25-dien-3 β -ol, 2a) have been isolated as their acetylated derivatives (1b and 2b respectively) from the marine green alga *Codium dwarkense*. 28-Isopufosterol (24Z-stigmasta-5,24(28)-dien-3 β -ol, 3), the major sterol of Ulvaceae family has been isolated both from *Ulva lactuca* and *U. reticulata*.

Marine algae of the genus *Codium* have been reported to be an important source of a wide variety of sterols and their oxygenated derivatives¹⁻⁵. Some oxygenated sterols of *Codium* sp. show cytotoxicity towards various cancer cell lines⁶. Methanol extract of *C. dwarkense* was found to have diuretic and anti-implantation activities⁷. The sterols from Ulvacean plants, of which 28-isopufosterol is known⁸ as the major constituent, were found to be responsible for the depression of blood pressure in human atherosclerosis and lowering of blood cholesterol level in rats and rabbits⁹. This prompted us to undertake the studies on sterol contents of some marine green algae from Indian waters which have not been studied so far.

Results and Discussion

Methanol-chloroform (7.5%) eluate of the methanol extract of *C. dwarkense* afforded on acetylation a sterol glycoside tetraacetate 1b. A 7% ethyl acetate-hexane eluate of the methanol extract of *C. dwarkense* afforded a free sterol 2a which has been identified as its acetate 2b. The free sterol 3 was obtained from the 7% ethyl acetate-hexane fractions of the methanol extracts of both *Ulva fasciata* and *U. reticulata*. We report herein the isolation and characterization of these sterols.

Compound 1b gave color reactions for sterol derivatives and the high value of its specific rotation indicated that it might contain a carbohydrate moiety. IR spectrum showed bands at 908, 1638 cm^{-1} for terminal methylene group¹ and a bands at 918 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of sugar moiety. ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound 1b showed the presence of 43 carbon atoms in the molecule, fourteen carbon signals corresponding to an acetylated hexose moiety and remaining 29 carbon signals due to the aglycone part.

The assignments of the carbon signals due to the aglycone are in good agreement with the reported ones¹⁰⁻¹². The anomeric carbon signal of the sugar moiety appeared at 99.6 ppm. A downfield signal at 80.3 ppm was attributed to C-3

showing the linkage of the sugar moiety at this carbon. The comparison of the chemical shift of the tetraacetylated sugar proton signals with those of reported ones^{13,14} suggested that the sugar moiety may be a galactose.

¹H NMR spectrum of **1b** showed the anomeric proton resonance as a doublet at 4.53 ppm (*J* 6.1 Hz). The signal for terminal methylene protons at C-26 appeared as broad singlets at 4.57 and 4.68 ppm. The attachment of sugar moiety shifted the carbinolic proton resonance of H-3 to 3.62 ppm¹⁰. ¹H NMR spectrum also showed the presence of an olefinic proton resonance as a broad singlet at 5.3 ppm which is the characteristic pattern of Δ^5 -sterol¹⁵. The sugar methylene protons (CH₂OCOCH₃) appeared as a broad doublet and a double doublet at 4.05 and 4.20 ppm, respectively.

In FABMS, fragments at *m/z* 95, 109, 149, 199, 213 and 255 confirmed the presence of sterol skeleton of the aglycone of compound **1b**^{16,17}. Fragments at *m/z* 109, 169 and 331 have been reported for β -D-galactopyranose pentaacetate¹⁸. The base peak at *m/z* 395 and a (M⁺ + Na) ion at *m/z* 765 (60%) indicated the molecular weight to be 742, corresponding to the molecular formula C₄₃H₆₆O₁₀. Therefore, the molecular formula of deacetylated derivative, sterol glycoside **1a** would be C₃₅H₅₈O₆, presumably the natural compound. From the foregoing physical and chemical evidence it is proposed that compound **1a** is a sterol glycoside. The compound under investigation was isolated as an acetate derivative and there has been consistent upfield shifts in the carbon resonance values in the glycone moiety with regard to the sterol glycoside of *C. iyengarii*⁹. This acetylated compound could not be deacetylated nor could it be hydrolyzed to get a free sugar moiety for confirmation. All attempts with base hydrolysis ended up in polymerization. Due to paucity of material further chemical studies on this could not be made. Attempts to isolate an underivatized sterol glycoside compound was also unsuccessful. However, from the above evidence and from biogenetic considerations, the provisional structure of the naturally occurring compound is proposed as 3-*O*- β -D-galactopyranosylstigmasta-5,25-diene **1a** (3-*O*- β -D-galactopyranosylclerosterol, C₃₅H₅₈O₆).

The free sterol **2a** was converted to its acetate **2b** for its identification. Based on the individual and m.m.p. (unsuppressed) determination, superimposable IR and similarities in the carbon-13 NMR and proton-NMR data with those available in the literature^{4,10,19}, the sterol acetate **2b** was identified as clerosterol acetate (24-ethyl cholesta-5,25-dien-3 β -ol acetate); therefore, the naturally occurring compound **2a** would be 24-ethyl cholesta-5,25-dien-3 β -ol.

Based on the individual and m.m.p. (unsuppressed) determination, superimposable IR and similarities in the carbon-13 NMR and proton-NMR as well as GC-MS data available in the literature^{11,19-23}, sterol **3** was identified as 28-isofucosterol (24*Z*-stigmasta-5,24(28)-dien-3 β -ol).

Experimental

Optical rotation was measured on a JASCO DIP-360 polarimeter. M.p. was measured on a Veego apparatus and is uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss Specord M80 spectrophotometer and proton and carbon-13 NMR (CDCl₃, at 400 and 100 MHz, respectively) on a Bruker WM-400 spectrometer equipped with an ASPECT 2000 computer using tetramethylsilane as internal standard. MS and FAB-MS were recorded on JEOL D-300 and JEOL JMS-SX 102 spectrometers, respectively, using xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas having accelerating voltage 10 kV at room temperature and *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol (NBA) as matrix. GC-MS of the free sterol was done on a Hewlett-Packard 5890 Series II machine connected to 5971A MSD machine, having a HP-5 capillary column running isothermally at 285° (injector temp. 250°; detector temp. 290°) using helium as carrier gas at the flow rate of 0.50 ml/min through the column. The EI mass-spectra were recorded at 70 eV.

C. dwarkense Boerg., (Family : Codiaceae), a green alga, was collected from Veraval (lat. 20° 54' N, long. 70° 22' E), at the West Coast of India. *U. reticulata* Forssk. and *U. lactuca* Linn. (Ulvaceae, Chlorophyta) were collected from Ervadi (lat. 9°25' N, long. 79°08' E) and Bet Dwarka (lat. 22°27' N, long. 69°12' E). After collection, algal materials were cleaned and washed with water, dried in shade and powdered. The powder was soaked in MeOH for 2 weeks and extracted with methanol at room temperature. The extract was evaporated under reduced pressure and the resulting dark green gummy residue was subjected to flash column chromatography for isolation of sterols.

Compound 1b : The methanol extract (30 g) of *C. dwarkense* was subjected to flash column chromatography (FCC) over 230–400 mesh silica gel (SRL, India) and eluted with mixtures of chloroform and methanol of different polarity. The 7.5% methanolic chloroform eluates, rich in one major spot on silica gel TLC plate (Merck silica gel GF254 precoated glass plates) visualized by iodine, were pooled and evaporated to give 4 g of extract which was acetylated with acetic anhydride-pyridine (1 : 1). Work-up of the reaction mixture gave the product (2.5 g). After repeated chromatographic purification, the acetylated product (360 mg

of white crystalline solid) was passed through alumina (neutral, grade IV) bed with 0.2–10% methanolic chloroform. The 0.5% methanolic chloroform eluate afforded white crystalline **1b** (0.037% dry wt. of alga), m.p. 168–170°; $[\alpha]_D - 74^\circ$ (c 0.05, MeOH); ν_{\max} 1750 (C=O, acetate), 1638 (terminal CH), 1220, 1162, 1102, 1052 (C-O-C), 980, 981 (sugar ring stretching), 908 cm^{-1} (terminal CH); $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 0.60 (s, H-18), 0.72 (t, 6.1 Hz, H-29), 0.83 (d, 6.1 Hz, H-21), 0.96 (s, H-19), 1.18 (s, H-26), 1.48 (s, H-26), 1.77, 1.83, 1.80 (br d, 6.1 Hz), 1.94 (s, COCH_3), 1.95 (s, COCH_3), 1.98 (s, COCH_3), 2.02 (s, COCH_3), 2.19 (m), 3.43 (m), 3.62 (double multiplet with fine splitting), 4.05 (br d, 12.0 Hz, H_a of sugar CH_2OAc), 4.20 (dd, 12 and 6 Hz, H_b of sugar CH_2OAc), 4.53 (d, 6.1 Hz, anomeric proton), 4.57 and 4.68 (br s each, terminal $=\text{CH}_2$), 4.90 (t, 6.1 Hz), 5.03 (t, 6.1 Hz), 5.15 (t, 6.1 Hz, H-6), 5.30 (br s, H-6); $^{13}\text{C NMR } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 11.8 (C-18), 12.0 (C-29), 17.8 (C-27), 18.6 (C-21), 19.3 (C-19), 20.7 (2',3',4',6' - CH_3COs), 2.11 (C-11), 24.3 (C-15), 26.5 (C-28), 28.1 (C-12), 29.4 (C-16), 29.6 (C-23), 31.9 (C-2,8), 33.7 (C-7,22), 35.5 (C-20), 36.7 (C-10), 37.2 (C-1), 38.9 (C-12), 39.8 (C-4), 42.3 (C-13), 49.5 (C-24), 50.2 (C-9), 56.1 (C-17), 56.8 (C-14), 62.1 (C-6'), 68.6 (C-4'), 71.6 (C-2'), 71.7 (C-5'), 73.0 (C-3'), 80.0 (C-3), 99.6 (C-1'), 111.3 (C-26), 122.1 (C-6), 140.4 (C-5), 147.6 (C-25), 170.3 (2',3',4',6' - CH_3COs); FAB-MS m/z 43 (30%), 55 (25%), 69 (15%), 81 (20%), 95 (20%), 109 (45%), 136 (20%), 154 (20%), 169 (60%), 213, 255 (10%), 289, 331 (55%), 395 (100%), 514, 532 (5%), 661 (10%), 683 (5%), 723, 741 (10%), 765 (60%), 862 (5%), 897 (10%).

Compound 2b : The methanol extract (18 g) of *C. dwarkense* on repeated flash column chromatography over 230–400 mesh silica gel afforded light green colored amorphous solid **2a** (800 mg) from 7% ethyl acetate-hexane eluates. It was acetylated with acetic anhydride-pyridine (1 : 1). Work-up and purification of the reaction mixture gave white crystalline compound **2b** (0.062% of dry alga), m.p. 125°; ν_{\max} 2940 (C-H), 1740 (CO-CH_3), 1450, 1380 (C-H bend), 1255, 1060 (C-O), 910 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 0.66 (s, H-18), 0.80 (t, 6.6 Hz, H-29), 0.90 (d, 6.6 Hz, H-21), 0.96 (s, H-19), 1.57 (s, H-26), 1.86 (m), 2.03 (s, COCH_3), 2.31 (d), 4.64 (br s, H_a -27), 4.72 (br s, H_b -27), 5.37 (br s, H-6); $^{13}\text{C NMR } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 11.8 (C-29), 12.0 (C-18), 17.9 (C-27), 18.6 (C-21), 19.3 (C-19), 21.3 (C-11), 24.2 (C-15), 26.5 (C-28), 28.1 (C-16), 29.5 (C-23), 31.9 (C-2, 8), 33.7 (C-7, 22), 35.5 (C-20), 36.6 (C-10), 37.0 (C-1), 39.1 (C-12), 42.3 (C-4, 13), 49.5 (C-24), 50.1 (C-9), 56.1 (C-17), 56.7 (C-14), 74.00 (C-3), 111.3

(C-26), 122.6 (C-6), 139.8 (C-5), 147.6 (C-25), 170.4 (COCH_3); FAB-MS (m/z) 42 (37%), 55 (72%), 69 (56%), 81 (44%), 95 (37%), 105 (32%), 120 (20%), 133 (12%), 147 (36%), 159 (16%), 213 (12%), 255 (10%), 310, 380 (12%), 394 (100%).

Compound 3 :

U. reticulata : The methanol extract (10 g) on repeated flash column chromatography over 230–400 mesh silica gel afforded light green colored amorphous solid (90 mg) from 7% ethyl acetate-hexane fraction. Repeated recrystallization from methanol afforded white crystalline compound **3** (70 mg, 0.009% of dry alga), m.p. 132–133°; ν_{\max} 3452 (O-H), 2935 (C-H), 1658 (C=C), 1463, 1443, 1378 (C-H bend), 1057 (C-O), 811, 670 cm^{-1} (C-H bend); $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 0.68 (s, H-18), 1.59 (d, H-29), 2.81 (q, H-25, 6.7 Hz), 3.54 (m, H-3), 5.10 (q, H-28), 5.35 (m, H-6); $^{13}\text{C NMR } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 12.3 (C-18), 13.1 (C-29), 19.2 (C-21), 19.8 (C-19), 21.5 (C-11, 26, 27), 24.7 (C-15), 28.4 (C-23), 28.6 (C-16), 29.0 (C-25), 32.0 (C-2), 32.3 (C-7, 8), 36.4 (C-22), 36.5 (C-20), 36.9 (C-10), 37.7 (C-1), 40.2 (C-12), 42.7 (C-4, 13), 50.6 (C-9), 56.5 (C-17), 57.2 (C-14), 72.2 (C-3), 116.9 (C-28), 122.0 (C-6), 141.2 (C-5), 146.3 (C-24); GC-MS ret. time 11.82 min (RRT 1.47, with respect to cholesterol at 8.11 min) m/z 55 (100%), 69, 83, 91, 105, 119, 131, 229, 281, 299, 314.

U. lactuca : The methanol extract (5 g) on repeated flash column chromatography over 230–400 mesh silica gel afforded light green colored amorphous solid **3** (40 mg) from 7% ethyl acetate-hexane eluates. Its repeated recrystallization from methanol afforded white crystalline compound (25 mg, 0.006% of dry alga), m.p. 132–133°; ν_{\max} 3452 (O-H), 2935 (C-H), 1658 (*cis* C=C stretch), 1462, 1443, 1377 (C-H bend), 1056 (C-O), 810, 669 cm^{-1} (*cis* C-H bend); $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 0.68 (s, H-18), 1.59 (d, H-29), 2.83 (q, 6.7 Hz, H-25), 3.51 (m, H-3), 5.10 (q, H-28), 5.35 (m, H-6); $^{13}\text{C NMR } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 12.3 (C-18), 13.1 (C-29), 19.2 (C-21), 19.8 (C-19), 21.5 (C-11, 26, 27), 24.3 (C-15), 28.4 (C-23), 28.6 (C-16), 29.0 (C-25), 32.0 (C-2), 32.3 (C-7, 8), 36.4 (C-22), 36.5 (C-20), 36.9 (C-10), 37.7 (C-1), 40.2 (C-12), 42.7 (C-4, 13), 50.6 (C-9), 56.4 (C-17), 57.2 (C-14), 72.2 (C-3), 116.9 (C-28), 122.1 (C-6), 141.2 (C-5), 146.6 (C-24); GC-MS ret. time 11.82 min (RRT 1.47, with respect to cholesterol at 8.11 min) m/z 55 (100%), 69 (88%), 83 (55%), 91 (56%), 105 (58%), 119 (33%), 131 (35%), 229 (46%), 281 (55%), 299 (48%), 314 (100%), 315 (39%).

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